

RUNNING HEAD: EEG and HRV jointly predict memory control

Resting-State Electroencephalogram and Heart Rate Variability Jointly Predict Intentional Episodic Memory Control Using Machine Learning Fusion

Xuelin Cheng, Na Xue, Yunfei Zhang, Jinhong Ding*

School of Psychology, Capital Normal University, No. 23 Bai Dui Zi Jia, HaiDian District, Beijing, 100037, P. R. China

*Correspondence: *Jinhong Ding (E-mail: dingjh@cnu.edu.cn).*

Supplemental Material

S1. Sensitivity Power Analysis

To post hoc justify our sample size and quantify the detectable effect size, a sensitivity analysis was performed using G*Power 3 (1). Since the primary aim of the study was to classify individuals into one of two independent groups (high vs. low memory control) using a machine learning approach, the statistical problem is analogous to detecting a significant difference between these groups in a high-dimensional feature space. The sensitivity analysis was therefore configured for an independent two-sample *t*-test. With α set to 0.05, statistical power ($1 - \beta$) set to 0.80, and sample sizes of $n = 21$ per group, the analysis indicated that this study was sufficiently powered to detect a minimum effect size of Cohen's $d = 0.88$. This represents a large effect size according to conventional benchmarks, demonstrating that the study design possessed adequate statistical power to detect robust effects of theoretical interest.

S2. Resting-state EEG and ECG Recording

EEG signals were recorded using a 64-channel Ag/AgCl electrode cap positioned according to the International 10-20 System (2), connected to a Neuroscan SynAmps2 amplifier system. The EEG was referenced online to the left mastoid. Concurrently, ECG signals were recorded via the same amplifier using a 2-lead channel placed below each clavicle. Data were sampled at 500 Hz, and all electrode impedances were maintained below 10 k Ω .

S3. EEG Preprocessing

Raw EEG data underwent preprocessing in EEGLAB (version 14.1.1) (3) within MATLAB using the following sequential pipeline: First, six electrodes (M1, M2, CB1, CB2) were excluded, retaining 60 channels for analysis. The data were then filtered with a 0.5 Hz high-pass filter, 30 Hz low-pass filter, and 48-52 Hz notch filter before

being re-referenced to the average of all 60 electrodes and downsampled to 250 Hz. Continuous recordings were segmented into 2-second non-overlapping epochs, excluding those from the first and last minutes to minimize initial acclimatization and terminal fatigue effects. Epochs containing significant artefacts were removed, and poor-quality channels were interpolated using spherical splines from neighboring channels. Subsequently, independent component analysis (ICA) was performed to remove residual contamination from ocular movements. Finally, to ensure consistent data quantity across participants, the first 84 artifact-free epochs per participant were selected for subsequent analysis.

S4. EEG Signal Quality Control and Denoising Validation

1. EEG Signal Quality Metrics

To quantify noise burden and preprocessing impact, we report the participant-level EEG quality-control (QC) metrics in Table S1:

Table S1. Descriptive statistics of EEG preprocessing quality-control metrics.

Metrics	Mean (SD)	Min	Max
Interpolated channels (n)	0.26 (1.04)	0	6.00
Rejected epochs (%)	0.92 (1.70)	0	6.67
ICA components removed (ocular, n)	1.69 (1.37)	0	8.00

2. EEG Denoising Validation

As a targeted quality-control check (not part of the main hypothesis tests), we examined two a priori denoising markers: frontal low-frequency power (0.5–2 Hz) as an index of ocular/slow-drift contamination, and parietal alpha-band power (8–13 Hz) as a marker of canonical resting-state structure. Low-frequency power was reduced after ICA, whereas alpha power was largely preserved. The results of Pearson correlations and *t*-test were reported below (see table S2 and S3)

Table S2. Paired-samples Pearson correlations between pre-ICA and post-ICA power indices.

Metric	Electrodes	N	Pearson r	<i>p</i>
Prefrontal low-frequency power	Fp1, Fpz, Fp2	42	0.07	0.66
Parietal alpha power	P3, P1, Pz, P2, P4	42	1.00	< 0.001

Note. *p*-values are two-tailed.

Table S3. Paired-samples *t*-test results for EEG denoising validation indices (pre-ICA vs. post-ICA, *N* = 42).

Metric	Pre-ICA Mean (SD)	Post-ICA Mean (SD)	Mean difference	95% CI of difference	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	Cohen's <i>d</i>
Prefrontal low-frequency power	108.72 (253.15)	9.21 (10.95)	99.51	[20.80, 178.23]	2.55	0.01	0.39
Parietal alpha power	5.46 (4.49)	5.44 (4.52)	0.02	[-0.02, 0.07]	1.18	0.24	0.18

Note. Mean difference is computed as pre-ICA – post-ICA; *p*-values are two-tailed.

S5. ECG Preprocessing

ECG data were processed using HRVanalysis (2). The raw signals underwent automated preprocessing, which included noise reduction and QRS complex detection, to derive the RR interval (RRI) time series (2). Artifact correction for ectopic beats and missing R peaks was performed using a two-stage approach. First, the software implemented automated correction, utilizing either cubic-spline interpolation or interpolation based on preceding valid RRI. Subsequently, all RRI data were visually inspected, and any remaining artifacts were manually corrected by identifying and marking the accurate R peaks within the ECG waveform.

S6. ECG Signal Quality Control and Denoising Validation

The underlying QRS detection approach of HRVanalysis software has been reported to achieve a 99.5% detection rate on the MIT-BIH arrhythmia database (2). Because RR-series editing is critical for valid HRV estimation, we additionally quantified the proportion of automatically corrected RR intervals (see table S4) and visually inspected all RR/ECG traces to manually correct any remaining mis-detections.

Table S4. ECG signal quality control: proportion of automatically corrected RR intervals.

Metrics	Mean (SD)	Min	Max
Automatically corrected RR intervals (%)	2.40 (4.25)	0	20

S7. Extracting EEG Features

Based on established evidence implicating frontal and parietal regions in memory control (4), we computed time- and frequency-domain features exclusively from electrodes within these regions. Furthermore, given the documented involvement of large-scale networks (particularly the attentional network) in memory control processes (4), we extracted microstate features from all electrodes to characterize the spatiotemporal dynamics of whole-brain network activity.

1. Time-Domain Amplitude Features

Time domain features were extracted from the EEG amplitude throughout the recording period. Specifically, we calculated six common time domain features: maximum, minimum, mean, standard deviation, kurtosis, and skewness. These metrics were derived from each epoch and then averaged across all epochs for each electrode, yielding six time-domain features per electrode.

2. Spectral Power Features

Preprocessed EEG data were transformed via fast Fourier transform (FFT) with 0.5 Hz frequency resolution. Spectral power (in μV^2) was calculated for each 2-second epoch, with values subsequently averaged across all epochs for each electrode. Total power and absolute power for four frequency bands were computed as the mean power within their respective ranges: delta (1–4 Hz), theta (4–8 Hz), alpha (8–13 Hz), and beta (13–30 Hz). Relative power for each band was additionally derived as the ratio of its absolute power to total power. Overall, this resulted in 8 power features per electrode: 4 frequency bands \times 2 metrics (absolute power, relative power).

3. Spectral Functional Connectivity Features

Spectral coherence was used as a metric of functional connectivity to reflect the synchronization of neural activities between two electrode sites. Coherence was computed as the ratio of the cross-spectral density of two signals to the product of their individual auto-spectral densities at each frequency point. Values range from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating stronger synchronization between the paired signals. For all frontal-parietal electrode pairs, coherence was computed per epoch at every frequency point and averaged across epochs. These frequency-specific values were then averaged within each predefined band, yielding one coherence value per frequency band per electrode pair.

4. Microstate Features

Microstate analysis was performed using the EEGLAB plugin. First, EEG data were bandpass-filtered between 2–20 Hz (5). For each participant, global field power (GFP) was computed as the standard deviation of EEG signals across electrodes at each time point. Since topographic maps with higher GFP exhibit greater topographic stability and lower signal-to-noise ratio, maps at local GFP peaks were identified as “original maps”.

Then, these original maps were clustered at the individual level using the atomize and agglomerate hierarchical clustering (AAHC) algorithm to derive four microstate templates. Consistent with prior research, four canonical microstate maps account for most topographic variance in resting-state EEG (6).

Following clustering, each participant’s EEG signal was represented as a time series of these four microstates, which were quantified using four parameters. Specifically, three key metrics were calculated for each microstate class: duration (in seconds, the average stability duration of a microstate), occurrence (per second, the average number of stable periods per second), and contribution (percentage of total recording time occupied by the microstate). These three features, computed across the four microstate classes, yielded 12 microstate features per participant. Additionally, transition probabilities between each pair of microstates were computed, yielding 12 additional features per participant.

S8. Extracting HRV Features

RRI signals from each participant were analyzed using time-domain, frequency-domain,

and nonlinear methods. Time-domain analysis calculated: SDNN (ms) (standard deviation of all normal-to-normal intervals, reflecting overall autonomic nervous system modulation); rMSSD (ms) (root mean square of successive RRI differences); and pNN50 (%) (percentage of successive RRI differences > 50 ms), with rMSSD and pNN50 specifically indicating parasympathetic activity. Frequency-domain analysis employed Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) on RRI signals resampled at 2 Hz, computing power within: very low frequencies (VLF, 0.003–0.04 Hz), low frequencies (LF, 0.04–0.15 Hz), high frequencies (HF, 0.15–0.4 Hz), and total frequencies (TP, 0.003–0.4 Hz, representing overall autonomic modulation). LF power reflects a mix of sympathetic and parasympathetic influences, while HF power specifically indicates parasympathetic modulation. Normalized units were derived—LFnu (defined in Equation 1) and HFnu (defined in Equation 2)—to quantify the relative contributions of the LF and HF spectral bands, respectively. The LF/HF ratio provided an estimate of sympathovagal balance. Nonlinear assessment included Poincaré plot analysis of consecutive RRI (RR_n vs. RR_{n+1}), generating SD1 (standard deviation perpendicular to $y = x$, reflecting short-term variability) and SD2 (standard deviation along $y = -x + 2 * \text{mean RR}$, representing long-term variability). Additionally, Shannon entropy was computed to quantify signal complexity, where higher values indicate uniformly distributed physiological patterns and lower values suggest probabilistic dominance of specific sequences. Finally, 13 HRV features were extracted.

$$LFnu = LF\ power / (TP - VLF\ power) * 100 \quad (1)$$

$$HFnu = HF\ power / (TP - VLF\ power) * 100 \quad (2)$$

S9. Key Modeling Settings for Unimodal Models

To facilitate reproducibility, Table S5 summarizes the LIBSVM options used to train the unimodal models. All options not listed here were left at the LIBSVM default settings and were applied consistently across unimodal EEG and HRV predictors.

Table S5. LIBSVM settings used in unimodal models

Option	Meaning	Value
-s	SVM type	3 (ϵ -SVR)
-t	Kernel type	3 (sigmoid)
-g	kernel scale parameter gamma; controls the nonlinearity/similarity width of the sigmoid kernel.	Grid [0.01, 10], step 0.01
-p	epsilon-insensitive loss width for ϵ -SVR (tolerance tube); errors within $\pm \epsilon$ incur no penalty	0.10
others	Remaining options	LIBSVM defaults

S10. Fusion weight sensitivity analysis

Because the weighted-sum rule can, in principle, be sensitive to the choice of fusion weight, we conducted a weight-sensitivity analysis to assess whether the observed fusion effects were robust across plausible weights rather than driven by a narrowly tuned setting. Here, $\alpha \in [0,1]$ denotes the EEG weight in the convex combination of unimodal prediction scores, such that the fused score is $S_{\text{fusion}} = \alpha S_{\text{EEG}} + (1 - \alpha) S_{\text{HRV}}$; therefore, smaller α corresponds to a more HRV-dominant fusion, and larger α places more emphasis on EEG.

Importantly, this analysis was used for robustness characterization only; α was not optimized or selected based on these results, and our inferential conclusions rely on the pre-specified AUC-based weighting rule and permutation tests.

Across fusion pairs, the AUC– α curves showed a similar monotonic pattern: performance was highest in an HRV-dominant regime (small α) and decreased as EEG weight increased. Equal-weight fusion ($\alpha = 0.5$) yielded AUCs comparable to the fusion with unimodal AUC-derived weights, and permutation tests indicated that the $\alpha = 0.5$ fusion typically improved over the corresponding EEG-only models (except the frontal time-domain EEG model) but not over the HRV-only model (Figure S1; Table S6).

Taken together, these results reflect a robust pattern in which HRV provides complementary information to EEG, yielding consistent improvements of the fused model over the EEG-only baseline across a plausible range of fusion weights. Notably, because α was not tuned under nested validation, we do not treat peak AUC values at any particular α as confirmatory evidence.

Table S6. AUC of equal-weight ($\alpha = 0.5$) EEG–HRV fusion models and permutation tests against unimodal baselines.

Fusion Models	AUC	P (Fusion > EEG)	P (Fusion > HRV)
EEG_Time domain_Frontal + HRV	0.857	0.113	0.724
EEG_Time domain_Parietal + HRV	0.830	0.020	0.724
EEG_Power_Frontal + HRV	0.844	0.020	0.724
EEG_Power_Parietal + HRV	0.803	0.015	0.724
EEG_Functional connectivity + HRV	0.927	0.009	0.724
EEG_Microstate + HRV	0.832	0.020	0.724

Note. P values were derived from a permutation test on fixed scores (5000 permutations): at each permutation, $\Delta AUC = AUC_{\text{fusion}} - AUC_{\text{single-modality}}$ was recomputed. Raw permutation p values correspond to $P(\Delta AUC_{\text{perm}} \geq \Delta AUC_{\text{obs}})$ (right-tailed; +1 correction). Multiple-comparison control was performed using the Benjamini–Hochberg false discovery rate procedure; adjusted p values (q values) are reported.

Reference

1. Faul F, Erdfelder E, Lang AG, Buchner A. G*Power 3: a flexible statistical power analysis program for the social, behavioral, and biomedical sciences. *Behav Res Methods* 39: 175–191, 2007. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03193146>.
2. Pichot V, Roche F, Celle S, Barthélémy JC, Chouchou F. HRVanalysis: a free software for analyzing cardiac autonomic activity. *Front Physiol* 7: 557, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2016.00557>.
3. Delorme A, Makeig S. EEGLAB: an open source toolbox for analysis of single-trial EEG dynamics including independent component analysis. *J Neurosci Methods* 134: 9–21, 2004. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jneumeth.2003.10.009>.
4. Yang W, Jia H, Feng Q, Wei D, Qiu J, Hulbert JC. Functional connectivity between right-lateralized ventrolateral prefrontal cortex and insula mediates reappraisal's link to memory control. *J Affect Disord* 290: 316–323, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2021.04.057>.
5. Koenig T, Prichet L, Lehmann D, Sosa PV, Braeker E, Kleinlogel H, Isenhardt R, John ER. Millisecond by millisecond, year by year: Normative EEG microstates and developmental stages. *Neuroimage* 16: 41–48, 2002. <https://doi.org/10.1006/nimg.2002.1070>.
6. Michel CM, Koenig T. EEG microstates as a tool for studying the temporal dynamics of whole-brain neuronal networks: A review. *Neuroimage* 180: 577–593, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2017.11.062>.